

Weak Mixing Angle in Weinberg-Salam Electroweak Model

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In this note a new form of Weinberg angle is discussed with using a new formula for calculating mass of w boson in terms of z boson and fine structure constant.

In 1967[1] Weinberg proposed his sketchy model which merges the weak and electromagnetic interaction into a single theory simply called as electroweak theory. Independently Salam also arrived at the conclusion that weak and electromagnetic force is the same force, simply suggesting unification. In Weinberg's theory four particles were needed as quanta of gauge field two w boson (+and -), one z boson and one photon. Except photon all other vector bosons get their mass from Higgs Mechanism[2]. Weak mixing angle or Weinberg angle (WA) θ_w It is the angle by which spontaneous symmetry breaking rotates the original W^0 and B^0 vector boson plane, producing as a result the Z^0 boson, and the photon. Simply WA is related to masses of w and z boson by

$$m_z = \frac{m_w}{\cos\theta_w}$$

In terms of $SU(2) \times U(1)$ coupling we similarly have

$$\cos\theta_w = \frac{g}{\sqrt{g^2 + g'^2}}$$

Mathematically [a]

$$\cos\theta_w = \frac{m_w}{m_z}$$

Recently we have proposed[3] a formula to calculate the mass of w boson in terms of fine structure constant and z boson mass, simply given by

$$M_w = \frac{2}{311} M_z \alpha^{-1}$$

If g is given by

$$g = \frac{4}{311\lambda} M_z \alpha^{-1}$$

If the Weinberg angle is given by

$$\sin^2\theta_w = 1 - \left(\frac{m_w^2}{m_z^2}\right)$$

Consequently we have

$$\sin^2\theta_w = 1 - \left(\frac{2\alpha^{-1}}{311}\right)^2$$

And the [a] is written as

$$\cos\theta_w = \frac{2\alpha^{-1}}{311}$$

One may substitute it into above other equations to get alternate equivalent forms.

References

[1] SW 1967 Phys. Rev. Letters Volume 19, Number 21, Pg-1264

[2] P.W. Higgs, Phys. Rev. Letters, 13, 508 (1964)

[3] Deep Jyoti Dutta. (2018). On The Fractional Fundamental Boson. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2551885>